

CHAPADA DO ARARIPE/BRAZIL AND CURRICULUM INTERNATIONALIZATION STRATEGIES IN PROMOTING ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8432204

Suiane Costa Alves

PhD student in Education at the PPG in Education at UNISINOS. Master in Science and Mathematics Teaching from UFC. Graduated in Chemistry from UECE. Professor of Chemistry Teaching Methodology UFC/UAB and SEDUC/CE. Member of the CEIE of UNISINOS. Email: suianealves@unisinós.br. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9103-617X>.

ABSTRACT

This work aims to reflect on the internationalization strategies in promoting sustainability from the study of Chapada do Araripe/Brazil. The theoretical assumptions adopted were Leask (2015), Lima and Alves (2022), Knight (2020), Romero (2006), Sarría (2006) and UNESCO (2016, 2021). Methodologically, a bibliographic research was developed, searching the main databases and digital repositories to support the proposed reflections. Finally, based on the results, we found out how important Chapada do Araripe is, which houses testimonies of ancient fauna and flora, of inestimable scientific value and recognized worldwide for its diverse fossil content. In this regard, the need to develop strategic actions that permeates the educational space as it collaborates for empowerment, stimulating student protagonism not only in the academic environment, but also in the various spaces for the exercise of environmental citizenship.

Keywords: Chapada do Araripe. Internationalization of Curriculum. Environmental Education.

1. Introduction

In the globalized world in which we live, the growing process of degradation of natural resources has motivated educators and researchers from all over the world to develop research that promotes environmental conservation in order to encourage the development of sustainable actions that focus on ecologically correct attitudes. (LIMA; ALVES, 2022). The global perception of human beings in promoting environmental citizenship refers to the feeling of belonging to a broader community and common humanity. It emphasizes the environmental,

political, economic, social and cultural interdependence and interconnection between local, national and global levels (UNESCO, 2016).

In this sense, educational institutions are committed to training students with the ability to act in the social sphere, developing sustainable actions and, in this context, Beneitone (2019) states that the curriculum must promote intercultural knowledge, developing skills and abilities, preparing students to fulfill themselves professionally, socially and economically in an international and intercultural context.

Working on Environmental Education (EA) from the Internationalization of the Curriculum (IoC) in an interdisciplinary perspective allows us to envision an education for everyone. Among the objectives to be achieved we have the action of ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education, promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all, as well as promoting global citizenship and the development of sustainable actions (UNESCO, 2021).

Reflecting on teaching strategies and their impact on learning consolidates the recognition that the educational space constitutes an environment of transformation that creates opportunities through the adequate performance of complex tasks, characterized by diversity, construction and socialization of knowledge. Having said that, the research question is related to the importance of Chapada do Araripe for the conservation of biodiversity in the Brazilian territory, with interdisciplinary work in EA based on the IoC being suggested, integrating Virtual Learning Environments (VLE) into the aforementioned process.

2 Environmental Education: guiding ideas for our reflection

The definition of the environment has always been linked to human development, consolidating itself from the interrelationship with natural space. According to Cachapuz *et. al.* (2005), we live in times marked by environmental degradation actions, resulting in consequences such as the depletion of natural resources and, in this context, the commitment to developing educational actions that prioritize education for sustainability becomes imperative.

Lopes and Tenório (2011) state that a Nation-State must be capable of harmonizing economic growth with social equity, enabling the preservation of natural heritage, guaranteeing its access for future generations. Indeed, when we talk about sustainability, we are invariably invited to reflect on environmental issues, since EA can and should be used as an instrument to raise awareness for biodiversity conservation.

In this sense, much has already been done in an attempt to preserve natural resources, however, it is clear that the path is still very long for us to arrive at an ideal model of society

that prioritizes a harmonious relationship with nature, focusing on actions that demonstrate the formation of the human person, as a citizen with rights and duties, in promoting sustainability in all its aspects.

According to Carreira (2020, p. 12), EE uses the environment that surrounds the individual as a tool and the concept of environment has transformed over time and in the different areas that deal with the topic. The need for survival permeated human actions in order to explore and understand nature, playing a fundamental role in their experiences, manifesting itself through observation, interaction and mimicry of natural phenomena. Looking generously at the natural space leads us to its understanding, as well as to understanding its transformations, contributing to the formation of global citizens.

From a collective perspective, environmental citizenship and global governance bring the concept of citizenship that highlights the participation of non-state actors in global decisions, especially those that have to do with the conservation of ecosystems, the preservation and control of contamination, as well as such as the adequate use of natural resources and social and business responsibility (VEGA, 2006). With the industrial revolution, the amplification of the process of aggression against the environment became evident, resulting in the need to deepen environmental discussions (MENDONÇA, 2012).

According to Romero (2006), citizens' concerns about the scarcity of natural resources and the increasing degradation of the environment have motivated reflections on the essential need for greater investment in EE at all levels of education. Rachel Carson's environmental alert, creation of the Club of Rome, Stockholm Conference, Rio- 92, Rio+20, among other historical milestones arise in the face of the imperative to think collectively about the preservation of natural resources.

The Club of Rome Report appears with the aim of raising awareness of the fact that natural resources are finite and that the capitalist way of life leads to a depletion of natural resources that ends up having social repercussions on the sectors of production of consumer goods. Thus, environmental impacts become the main topic of discussion at the meeting to create the Club of Rome (LIMA; ALVES, 2022, p. 25).

In this way, the EE approach is referenced through contextualized and interdisciplinary work, committed to citizenship training at all levels of education, promoting reflections around understanding and overcoming the environmental crisis (LIMA; ALVES, 2022).

The consolidation of global citizenship at the local, regional and global level contributes to the integral development of human beings that involves the IoC process, meeting global needs and demands, being considered a strategic plan (KNIGHT, 2020), articulating knowledge

and practices with guidance interdisciplinary. Dialoguing with the IoC process, Knight (2020) states that international learning is a process of cooperation and exchange that ends up impacting the way content is worked on, motivating the development of creative thinking, cooperation and gratitude.

In this sense, the international dimension of the curriculum has advanced from an approach focused on area studies or regional studies and foreign languages to the integration of international, global, intercultural and comparative perspectives into the teaching/learning process and programmatic content. (KNIGHT, 2020, p. 19)

In this process, interdisciplinarity constitutes an extremely valuable tool in facing problem situations of a global nature, whose materiality allows the contextualization of everyday situations (FAZENDA, 2007), problematizing emerging issues in society, dialoguing with the IoC. This is where the role of Sciences is configured in this construction that overlaps actions of daily life, where it is capable of helping the student to improve their knowledge, promoting their intellectual development, the understanding of concepts and methodological procedures associated with attitudes and values (BRAZIL, 2018).

Among the areas in constant expansion, Environmental Chemistry, also known as Green Chemistry, is characterized by the training need of citizens for sustainability and responsible action in relation to the conservation of natural resources and biodiversity, maintenance of ecosystems, disposal of chemical waste toxic substances, water and soil treatment, among other topics, which constitute this training path (FELICIANO; ARIZA, 2019).

To assist in the process of expansion and consolidation of EA, Brazilian education relies on official documents that guide the teaching and learning process, identified as follows: Law of Guidelines and Bases (LDB) nº 9394 of 1996, National Curricular Parameters (PCN) of 1999, National Curricular Guidelines (DCN) of 1999 and, currently, the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) of 2018. Law nº 9795/1999, set out in CNE/CP Opinion nº 14/2012, also stands out in EA. and in Resolution CNE/CP nº 2/2012. It is noteworthy that, at BNCC, the theme of EE is covered in skills of the curricular components, and it is up to the education systems and schools, according to their specificities, to deal with it in a contextualized way.

3 Biodiversity and Geomorphology of Chapada do Araripe/Brazil

Chapada do Araripe is located in the Caatinga domain, covering part of the states of Ceará, Pernambuco and Piauí, Northeast region of Brazil (Figure 1), being considered one of

the most important reliefs in the region (TAVARES FILHO et al., 2020 *apud* SOUZA et. al. , 2021, p. 2). A location of extreme importance and invaluable scientific value and recognized worldwide for its diverse fossil content and exceptional preservation (SANTOS et al., 2020 *apud* SOUZA et. al . 2021, p. 2).

Chapada do Araripe had its origin, from a geomorphological point of view, associated with the rifting and subsequent division of Gondwana, in the Cretaceous. Tectonic activities were associated with the flexural uplift of the interior of the continent, with subsidence in the coastal zone, which led to the construction of a vast amphitheater, between the Parnaíba sedimentary basin and the Borborema massif. (SILVA NETO, 2013, p. 56)

For Silva Neto (2013), marshes appear both in crystalline areas and in sedimentary areas, such as Chapada do Araripe, which are geomorphological features highlighted topographically in relation to the Sertaneja Depression, inserted in the state of Ceará or which serve to delimit it with the states neighbors. The diversity of native vegetation in Chapada do Araripe follows the elevation variations and the exposure of the slopes to the humid winds that blow from the northern quadrant.

According to Bastos et. al (2016), the Araripe Basin is the most extensive sedimentary basin in the interior of Northeastern Brazil and its limit does not only extend to Chapada do Araripe, as it also incorporates the Cariri Valley, totaling an area of approximately 9,000km².

In the Cariri Valley there are typical reliefs of sedimentary basins such as plateaus, test hills and peripheral depressions. Considering its size and arrangement in relation to atmospheric circulation systems, this basin presents significant climatic variety, especially from a rainfall point of view, justifying the presence of humid sectors, on the eastern slopes, and dry sectors, in the opposite direction. (BASTOS, et. al. , 2016, p. 2).

Figure 1: Location map of Chapada do Araripe, Brazil

Source: Bastos *et. al*, 2016.

In Chapada do Araripe, the plant formations of shrubby and arboreal caatinga, Carrasco, Cerradão, Cerrado and Mata Úmida can be distinguished, in addition to a strip of Cerradão Carrasco. In the swamps, where there is greater biodiversity and diverse plant formations, typical of the different botanical morphoclimatic domains of the Brazilian territory, which should be preserved, as they represent a richness integrated into the natural environment around them, interacting with surface and underground drainage, there is a strong demand for the use of natural resources (SILVA NETO, 2013, p. 29). Thus, in the Cariri valley, below 600m altitude, the native vegetation, due to occupation, was soon replaced by polyculture, cotton farming, banana farming and sugarcane plantations. The practice of rustic carpentry is also observed using native wood, mainly in the section of the National Forest belonging to the municipality of Barbalha, located in Ceará.

In this regard, it is important to highlight the loss of native vegetation in a total of 39,333.09ha belonging to the Araripe National Forest (FLONA), distributed among the

municipalities of Santana do Cariri, Nova Olinda, Crato, Barbalha, Missão Velha and Jardim (SILVA NETO , 2013). Internationalization, according to Jardel (2019), is a process that responds to the dynamics of interaction that develops in an increasingly globalized world, which also includes the concept of global citizenship in education, promoting the conservation of geological heritage of humanity, which declares itself as part of the global UNESCO project.

Geological heritage is a set of non-renewable natural resources that, having scientific, cultural, pedagogical and tourist value, allows knowledge, study and interpretation of the Earth's geological history, as well as the processes that have shaped and continue to shape it. (BRILHA, 2005 apud CORDEIRO *et. al.* 2014, p. 7).

In the western portion of Chapada, more inland and depressed, there is a predominance of arboreal caatinga on the limits of the escarpments, both those facing Ceará and those that stand out in the lowered areas of the states of Pernambuco and Piauí. (SILVA NETO, 2013, p. 63)

Thus, knowing the climatic and geomorphological characteristics makes it possible to expand the conservation process in its region of coverage, contributing to an environmental protection framework for biodiversity. Through the diagnosis of environmental vulnerability of Chapada do Araripe, EA is envisioned through the promotion of sustainable actions in order to minimize environmental impacts in the study area in question.

4 The Internationalization of the Curriculum and Teaching Strategies

Reflecting on the IoC process invariably invites us to deepen the theory, being the object of discussion of this topic. According to Leask (2015), IoC is an essential component of the internationalization of education, whose impact is on student learning, which becomes deeper if: 1) Attention is given to the Internationalization of the Curriculum based on learning; 2) The approach goes beyond isolation, with experiences and activities; 3) The process is carried out in a planned and systematic manner (LEASK, 2015).

When Leask (2015) answers the question “ Why internationalize the Curriculum?”, The author defends internationalization as fundamental to strengthening global education, which seeks to prioritize respect and unity between different cultures, bringing people and nations together.

Along this path, the five stages of IoC are presented (LEASK, 2015), arranged in the following sequence: 1) review and reflect; 2) imagine; 3) review and plan; 4) act; 5) evaluate. Working on IoC Strategies in EA based on the Study of Chapada do Araripe allows us, from

the literature review and the study of environmental impacts, to reflect on the importance of the topic in question, leading the student to plan and think about possible solutions to the environmental impacts suffered, promoting the application and evaluation and, if necessary, the replanning of the aforementioned process. This construction relies on the use of applications and digital information systems that expand the theoretical framework and enable the student to immerse themselves in the process of developing their own knowledge.

Teaching strategies seek to deepen and expand actions aimed at improving pedagogical praxis, with shared and participatory management as a guideline. This construction involves a commitment to comprehensive education, which, according to UNESCO (2016), aims to promote training for global citizenship by encouraging application in real life, emphasizing the importance of the context to give meaning to what is learned and the protagonism of students in their learning and in the construction of their life project.

In *Education for global citizenship: topics and learning objectives*, UNESCO (2016) discusses integral education and provides educators with pedagogical information that impacts the curricular planning of activities and is the result of a long research process in different contexts geographical and sociocultural.

Global citizenship refers to the feeling of belonging to a broader community and common humanity. It emphasizes political, economic, social and cultural interdependence and interconnection between local, national and global levels. (UNESCO, 2016, p. 14).

Established as one of the education priorities according to UNESCO (2016), this action aims to promote the strengthening of student protagonism, the exercise of global citizenship, preparation for the world of work, as well as the strengthening of academic training, in order to guarantee the continuity of studies. In the process of consolidating knowledge in EA, making use of ecological trails and experimental practices constitute pedagogical tools that encourage creativity, research and the exchange of information, stimulating the development of investigative feeling.

In relation to teaching strategies based on a diversified curriculum, the aforementioned study involves knowledge related in the sequence: 1) General chemistry, biochemistry and experimental practices; 2) Production of geographic maps, cartography and geomorphology; 3) Study of environmental impacts and biodiversity. The identification of changes in the geographic space of Chapada do Araripe can be carried out using Landsat-5 images and the Geographic Information System (GIS) such as, for example, SPRING and TERRAVIEW,

through which it is possible to produce geographic maps with the identification of possible degradations (ALVES, 2022).

According to Sarria (2006), the term Geographic Information System (GIS) usually applies to computer systems aimed at managing spatial data, which constitute the most appropriate and extended computer tool for research and professional work in Science. Earth and Environmental. GIS is a complex tool and a reflection of the complexity of the object of study of this science, the result of scientific and technological development and is known as Geographic Information Science (SARRIA, 2006). Next, it is possible to view the image with the approximate limits of Chapada do Araripe and the Landsat image quadrant (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Image with approximate limits of Chapada do Araripe and quadrant of the Landsat image

Source: Silva Neto, 2013

Making use of GIS in environmental studies allows students to immerse themselves in the area of study under analysis, where it is possible through orbital images, obtained from remote sensing techniques, a detailed analysis, with the collection of specific information and the planning of more complex strategies. environmental conservation assertion (ALVES, 2022).

It is noteworthy that the set of sciences involved in the production of maps are Geodesy, Cartography, Geography, Geology, Ecology, etc., have developed a broad set of techniques to map the acts of the Earth's surface (SARRIA, 2006). In this context, remote sensing of natural resources is based on a remote data acquisition system about the biosphere, which is based on the properties of electromagnetic radiation and its interaction with materials on the Earth's surface (ROMERO, 2006).

In relation to the use of technological devices, GIS and AVA, based on the experience of French didactics with the Theory of Didactic Situations (TSD) by Guy Brousseau (2008), it is possible to align teaching contents and educational methods, addressing the didactics as a field of investigation whose object is the communication of knowledge. In this sense, working on EA aligned with technological devices using different methodologies allows us to envision the promotion of integral education. The application of TSD in relation to this work can be done through the use of virtual learning platforms and experiments, based on the elaboration of theoretical activities and laboratory practices.

The use of experimentation to contextualize content with an environmental focus allows the student to relate to the experiment and their daily lives, connecting them to theoretical concepts. For Hernandez and Basurto (2018, p. 51 - own translation)³, “knowledge is in everyday reality and the student, in contact with it, can spontaneously ascend to it”. Thus, dialogue about everyday topics that can interact with the reality experienced by the student can lead them to more meaningful learning.

In this sense, among the far-reaching virtual platforms, we can mention the virtual learning environment AVACED, linked to the Department of Education of the State of Ceará (SEDUC/CE) and the Coordination of Distance Education (CODED). AVACED is a Moodle environment whose mission is to promote extension courses for public school teachers and students, with a focus on improving the quality of learning.

Teaching practice constitutes a complex action, with a view to training the student based on a diverse curriculum that strengthens actions, such as the contextualized and interdisciplinary treatment of content, fostering fundamental educational attitudes to expand the countless possibilities of interaction.

Making use of ecological trails, experimental practices and technological devices in the student training process, we envision a deepening of action-reflection, such as the need for

³“ The knowledge is in everyday reality and the student, in contact with it, can rise spontaneously to it ”.

interdisciplinary dialogue, based on the premises of IoC based on the use of diversified methodologies in order to meet the specific needs of students in promoting global citizenship.

Therefore, there are many challenges in environmental education and they occur in an attempt to develop skills and abilities that allow greater educator-student and student-everyday interaction. Thus, the didactic transposition of knowledge can enable contextualized and interdisciplinary dialogue with a view to environmental sustainability.

5 Final Considerations

During this research, considerations about the importance of IoC in EA based on interdisciplinary work permeated the discussions, aligned with the development of strategic actions. In this way, it sparked reflection on the role of education and educational institutions in the development of sustainable actions. Enabling such discussions aims to remodel pedagogical practice, prioritizing contextualization and project development, impacting communities in promoting global citizenship.

The process of training students based on a diverse curriculum is a very valuable tool, as it allows for constant dialogue between theory and practice. In times when new research and technologies emerge every day, observing the impact on the environmental area to motivate students towards new teaching strategies helps them to be willing to learn.

In this sense, reflecting on the process of Internationalization of the Curriculum based on the study of Chapada do Araripe/Brazil emerges as an instrument capable of enhancing learning in EA, providing opportunities for new ways of doing Science, contributing to citizenship training, as well as strengthening the student protagonism and intellectual autonomy.

References

ALVES, SC Biodiversity of the Serra de Aratanha: interdisciplinary work based on the use of the internationalization of the curriculum. In: CAVALCANTE, Ana Geovanda Mourão et. al. (org.). **Education for the 21st Century and the MAIS PAIC Program** : Training Paths within the Scope of CREDE 1, ed. CRV, 2022.

BASTOS, F. de H.; CORDEIRO, AMN; MACEDO, FE; AZEVEDO, R ES de. Environmental management in the landscapes of the Araripe basin in the State of Ceará . **Revista Franco-Brasileira de Geografia** , n 29, 2016. Available at: <https://journals.openedition.org/confins/11509>. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

BENEITONE, Pablo. **Internationalization of the curriculum** : case studies in Argentine universities. 2019 Thesis (Doctorate in Social Sciences) – Faculty Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Argentina, 2019. Available at: <https://repositorio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/handle/10469/16436>. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

BRAZIL. Ministry of Education. **Common National Curriculum Base**. Brasília, DF: Ministry of Education, 2018. Available at: <http://basenacionalcomum.mec.gov.br/>. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

BROUSSEAU, G. **Introduction to the study of didactic situations**: contents and teaching methods. São Paulo: Ática, 2008.

CACHAPUZ, A.; GIL-PEREZ, D.; PERSONA DE CARVALHO, AM; PRAIA, J.; • VILCHES, A. **The necessary renewal of science teaching** / António Cachapuz...[et al.], (organizers) — São Paulo: Cortez, 2005. *E-book*. Available at: <http://professor.pucgoias.edu.br/SiteDocente/admin/arquivosUpload/17569/material/T.5-%20A%20NECESS%C3%81RIA%20RENOVA%C3%87%C3%83O%20DO%20ENSINO%20DAS%20CI%C3%84NCIAS.pdf>. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

CARREIRA, R. The role of Environmental Education in the execution of public policies. **Journal of Science and Mathematics Teaching**, v. 11, no. 2, p. 11-23, 30 Mar. 2020 . Available at: <https://revistapos.cruzeirodosul.edu.br/index.php/rencima/article/view/2716>. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

CORDEIRO, AMN; BASTOS, F. de H. Geotouristic potential of the state of Ceará, Brazil. **Culture and Tourism Magazine - CULTUR** , YEAR 8 - Nº 02 -JUL, 2014. Available at: <https://periodicos.uesc.br/index.php/cultur/article/view/2302>. Accessed on: 08 Mar. 2023.

FAZENDA, I. **Interdisciplinarity**: a partnership project. 6. ed. São Paulo: Loiola, [1991] 2007.

FELICIANO, JMO; ARIZA, LGA Mobilidad Internacional Brazil – Colombia: green chemistry in the training of chemistry teachers. **Chemical Education in Point of View** : Latin American Chemical Education Research Network – ReLAPEQ, [s. l .], v. 3, no. 1, 2019. Available at: <https://revistas.unila.edu.br/eqpv/article/view/1606>. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

HERNÁNDEZ, ER; BASURTO, GR Teaching in science. a look at reflection . **CINZONTLE** , year 12, No. 26, June, 2018. Available at: <https://revistas.ujat.mx/index.php/Cinzontle/article/view/2216> Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

JARDEL, AJR Internationalization in higher education; administrative, academic and training processes. **Journal homepage** , 2019. Available at: <https://periodicos.unis.edu.br/index.php/mythos/article/view/304>. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

KNIGHT, J. **Internationalization of higher education**: concepts, trends and challenges. São Leopoldo: Oikos, 2020.

LEASK, B. **Internationalizing the curriculum**. United States, British Library, 2015.

LIMA, IB; ALVES, SC **Environmental education and interdisciplinarity**: from the explanation of concepts in the PCNs and DCNEM to pedagogical practice in high school. State University of Ceará , EdUECE, 2022.

LOPES, U.; TENÓRIO, R. **Education as the Foundation of Sustainability**. Salvador: EDUFBA, 2011.

MENDONÇA, R. **Environment and Nature** . São Paulo: Senac, 2012.

ROMERO, Francisco Sacristán. Satellite teledetection and environmental protection systems. **Scientific journal of the Spanish Acuiculture Society – AquaTIC** [s. l .], n° 24 – 2006. Available at: http://www.revistaaquatic.com/aquatic/pdf/24_02.pdf. Accessed on: 03 Mar. 2023.

SARRIA, FA **Geographic Information System** . University of Murcia. Ukraine, 2006. Available at: <https://www.um.es/geograf/sigmur/sigpdf/temario.pdf>. Accessed on: 06 Mar. 2022.

SILVA NETO, B. **Loss of natural vegetation in Chapada do Araripe (1975/2007) in the state of Ceará**. Thesis (Doctorate in Geography). São Paulo: São Paulo State University (UNESP). Institute of Geosciences and Exact Sciences, 2013. Available at: https://repositorio.unesp.br/bitstream/handle/11449/104464/silvaneto_b_dr_rcla.pdf?sequence=1#:~:text=Os%20resultados%20obtidos%20mostraram%20a,produces%C3%A7%C3%A3o%20de%20firewood%20and%20charcoal%C3%A3o. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

SOUZA, FGLS de; SILVA, MAP da.; LOIOLA, MIB Passifloraceae ss in Chapada do Araripe, northeastern Brazil. **Brazilian Journal of Physical Geography** v.14, n.02, 2021. Available at: <https://periodicos.ufpe.br/revistas/rbgfe/article/view/246656>. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

UNESCO. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. **Build peace in the minds of men and women**. Brasilia: UNESCO-ABIPTI, 2021. Available at: <https://pt.unesco.org/fieldoffice/brasilvia/expertise/education-2030-brazil>. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

UNESCO. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. **Rethinking Education: towards a global common good?** . Brasilia: UNESCO – ABIPTI, 2016. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000244670>. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.

, R.P. Global environmental citizenship. An analytical approach to the study of transnational civil society. **Spiral (Guadalaj.)** [n. l .], vol.12 no.35 Guadalajara ene./abr. 2006. Available at: https://www.scielo.org.mx/scielo.php?pid=S1665-05652006000100006&script=sci_abstract. Accessed on: May 7, 2023.